

Project start date: 01/01/2022 | Duration: 36 months

D3.2 – GreenSCENT apps: Technical architecture and user guide, including UI and accessibility

Due date of the Deliverable: 31-12-2023
Actual submission date: 20-12-2023

Project	GreenSCENT – Smart Citizen Education for a Green Future
Call ID	H2020-LC-GD-2020-3-2020
Work Package	WP3 – Digital Demonstrators (iterative) Development
Work Package Leader	Engineering Ingegneria Informatica ENG
Deliverable Leader	Engineering Ingegneria Informatica ENG
Deliverable coordinator	Vladimiro Scotto di Carlo (ENG) – vladimiro.scottodicarlo@eng.it
Deliverable Nature	R
Dissemination level	PU
Version	1.0
Revision	Final

1. Document Info

1.1. Authors

Author name	Organization Acr.	E-mail
Vladimiro Scotto di Carlo	ENG	vladimiro.scottodicarlo@eng.it
Alessandra Aurelio	ENG	alessandra.aurelio@eng.it

1.2. Contributors

Contributor name	Organization Acr.	E-mail

1.3. Reviewers

Reviewers name	Organization Acr.	E-mail
Sarah Anne Mc Donagh	UAB	sarahanne.mcdonagh@uab.cat
Mattias Friis Jørgensen	DBT	mfi@tekno.dk

1.4. Document History

Version #	Author/s	Date	Changes
0.1	Alessandra Aurelio	01/10/2023	Finalized Table of Content
0.2	Vladimiro Scotto di Carlo Alessandra Aurelio	10/10/2023	Finalized architecture section Started user guide section
0.3	Alessandra Aurelio	16/10/2023	Installation and set up section Key features section Refinements and improvements
0.4	Vladimiro Scotto di Carlo	17/10/2023	Accessibility section Refinements and improvements
0.5	Alessandra Aurelio	20/10/2023	Minor changes
0.6	Vladimiro Scotto di Carlo	09/11/23	Refinements and improvements
0.7	Vladimiro Scotto di Carlo	02/12/2023	Document updated with the contributions received from DBT and UAB (peer review)
1.0	Vladimiro Scotto di Carlo	20/12/2023	Final release

1.5. Document data

Keywords	<i>App, mobile, environment, report, territory</i>
Editor address data	Name: Vladimiro Scotto di Carlo Partner: ENG Address: Torre Saverio Isola C1 Centro Direzionale, 80143 Napoli Phone: +393479022570 Email: vladimiro.scottodicarlo@eng.it
Peer Review date	02-12-2023
Submission date	22-12-2023

1.6. Table of Contents

1. DOCUMENT INFO	2
1.1. AUTHORS	2
1.2. CONTRIBUTORS	2
1.3. REVIEWERS	2
1.4. DOCUMENT HISTORY	2
1.5. DOCUMENT DATA	2
1.6. TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	3
1.6.1. <i>List of Tables</i>	4
1.6.2. <i>List of Figures</i>	4
1.7. ACRONYMS.....	5
1.8. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	6
2. INTRODUCTION	7
3. ENVIRONMENT MONITORING MOBILE APP HANDBOOK.....	8
3.1. <i>Purpose of the document</i>	8
3.2. <i>Type of users</i>	8
3.3. <i>Use cases</i>	9
3.4. <i>Installation and set-up</i>	10
3.5. <i>Key features</i>	13
3.5.1. <i>Select Domain (Institution)</i>	13
3.5.2. <i>Homepage and user interface structure</i>	15
3.5.3. <i>List View</i>	18
3.5.4. <i>Maps View</i>	20
3.5.5. <i>Detail page</i>	20
3.5.6. <i>Personal View</i>	22
3.5.7. <i>New Report View</i>	23
3.6. <i>System requirements</i>	25
4. APP ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW	26
4.1. <i>Presentation Layer</i>	27
4.2. <i>Application Layer</i>	29
4.3. <i>Database Layer</i>	29
5. ACCESSIBILITY FEATURES	32
5.1. <i>Languages supported</i>	32
5.2. <i>Other accessibility features</i>	33
6. CONCLUSION	36

1.6.1. List of Tables

Table 1 – Environmental reports transition state	9
--	---

1.6.2. List of Figures

Figure 1 - Workflow of states of the reports	10
Figure 2- iOS installation procedure, step 1 and 2	11
Figure 3- iOS installation procedure, step 3	11
Figure 4- iOS installation procedure, step 4	12
Figure 5- Geolocation on Android devices	13
Figure 6- App landing view	14
Figure 7 – Homepage before/without authentication	15
Figure 8- User interface structure	16
Figure 9- Top Navigation Bar	16
Figure 10- Authentication using the TOP Navbar	17
Figure 11- The bottom Navigation Bar	17
Figure 12- LIST View	18
Figure 13- Tags	19
Figure 14- Report card	19
Figure 15 – Map View	20
Figure 16 – Detail of a report	21
Figure 17 – Workflow feature	21
Figure 18- Icon bar	22
Figure 19- Personal view	23
Figure 20- + button on the Bottom Navigation Bar	23
Figure 21- NEW REPORT VIEW	24
Figure 22 – GreenSCENT Platform overall architecture	26
Figure 23 – MERN stack (source: bigscal.com)	27
Figure 24 – 3 Tier architecture convention	27
Figure 25 – Frontend components	28
Figure 26- MongoDB main characteristics (source: MongoDB)	31
Figure 27- Language choice dialog	32
Figure 28- New View in Greek	33
Figure 29- Example of the Main page (List view) on iOS with colour inversion option enabled.	35

1.7. Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CRDP	United Nations' Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities
EAB	External Advisory Board
EAC	Exploitation Advisory Committee
EC	European Commission
ECAS	European Commission Authentication System
EPM	Executive Project Management
GA	General Assembly
IMB	Innovation Management Board
MB	Management Board
PC	Project Coordinator
PU	Public Document
UI	User Interface
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WP	Work Package

1.8. Executive Summary

This document reports the technical architecture of the Environmental Monitoring app that is the demonstrator developed in the T3.3 of WP3. It describes the main components, their interactions, and the features that each one offers. Moreover, it provides a user guide about installation and use of the app.

Most components are considered as black boxes, so the details of their inner architecture are not described. However, some components are further detailed to highlight the most relevant features of the system, such as scalability or performance.

The UI is described in detail, so the document can be considered as a handbook for the mobile app as well.

2. Introduction

GreenSCENT – Smart Citizen Education for a Green Future – is a research and innovation project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under Grant Agreement N° 101036480. GreenSCENT aims at developing a competence framework embracing all the Green Deal focus areas through an iterative, participatory, experience and learning-by-doing based design approach. GreenSCENT activities embrace both experts' and researchers' inputs and advice, citizen participation and stakeholder engagement initiatives; different European regions, different educational levels (from primary schools to higher education), at different engagement levels (from observation to data collection and processing, to contribute to scientific and policy agenda). GreenSCENT legacy will consist of the GreenSCENT Competence Framework, its Methodology, Use Cases, User Guides; Training kits co-designed for implementing the framework; the set of digital, physical and hybrid demonstrators developed by the project; and ECCEL, a European “driving license” for Climate and Environmental competencies and skills, that will be tested during the project.

In the EU Green Deal context, our focus extends comprehensively across various dimensions, notably impacting pilot sites distributed across the EU. These pilot sites encompass educational institutions within our consortium and, importantly, engage the wider European public. At the core of this initiative there is the Environmental Monitoring Mobile App that is part of the set of demonstrators, and it is an application designed to empower registered users to systematically generate detailed geolocated environmental reports: the app has been designed to allow the gathering of environmental reports from citizens in the territory, so it is fundamentally aimed at optimizing the communication and coordination of a group of individuals. It implements a seamless pipeline that can effectively show, store, and manage various types of. Each report is meticulously structured, featuring a title for identification, a detailed problem description, and substantiating visual evidence in the form of images or videos. These reports are georeferenced and categorized based on predefined criticality types, such as Risk, Emergency, Pollution, and Solution.

The application incorporates a map-based display of reports using their own geographical coordinates. This spatial representation adds a layer of clarity to the criticality and distribution of reported environmental issues. To manage the lifecycle of each report, a dedicated workflow has been implemented, ensuring efficient state changes management.

On the technical front, the application serves as a robust platform, enabling users to create environmental reports seamlessly and update their status dynamically. This real-time interaction mechanism is pivotal in maintaining the relevance and accuracy of environmental information. The generated environmental reports and their status updates form a collective repository that significantly contributes to building environmental awareness. This awareness is not passive but represents an evolving understanding of environmental challenges, driven by the continuous flow of data and insights.

This document - GreenSCENT apps: Technical architecture and user guide, including UI and accessibility – serves as a comprehensive guide to the technical architecture and user-related aspects of the *Environmental Monitoring Mobile App*.

The contents of this document can be summarised as follows:

- **Chapter 3** provides guidance on how to install and use the app. This section describes all the interfaces in terms of how to interact with the app, the features available and how to perform an action, etc.
- **Chapter 4** details the architecture designed for Environmental Monitoring App, its place in the global GreenSCENT architecture and the main components, involved in mobile app features.
- **Chapter 5** is a section dedicated to the *Accessibility features* and it is about how the application has been designed to be user-friendly for individuals with diverse abilities.

3. Environment Monitoring Mobile App Handbook

3.1. Purpose of the document

This document serves as a **comprehensive guide to the technical architecture and user-related aspects** of the *Environmental Monitoring Mobile App*. It is designed to provide detailed insights for users and particular aspects related to the technical architecture that support the application.

The target audience are the people from the cultural institution who want to better understand the features of the app and all people involved in the project that want learn more about the functioning and potential of the mobile app.

The mobile app empowers registered users to generate comprehensive environmental reports. Each report includes a title, a description of the issue, along with visual evidence in the form of images or videos. All reports are georeferenced and categorized based on predefined criticality types, such as Risk, Emergency, Pollution, and Solution. The application also provides a map-based display of reports using their respective coordinates.

Mobile app requirements and future scenarios have been investigated during the Youth Assemblies in February 2023. The method and outputs are described in the deliverable D3.1 (GreenSCENT-D3.1 Interaction Design).

3.2. Type of users

The app is based on the idea that the services shall be made accessible to educational "institutions" (schools, universities, associations of citizens, etc...). Each institution has its own space on the platform and its own set of registered users among which there will be an administrator who coordinates the community.

The GreenSCENT web platform offers different levels of access and permissions to its users, based on their user type and responsibilities. This helps ensure that users can perform their tasks effectively and efficiently, while maintaining the security and integrity of the platform.

The types of users managed by GreenSCENT are the following:

- **Institution administrators:** They act as administrators for their respective institutions and are responsible for managing new registration requests, creating and/or annotating content, and managing environmental reports. Each institution can have only one defined administrator user.
- **Institution associated users (standard users):** These users belong to an institution for which they have requested registration and are authorized to collaborate by creating several types of content such as videos, images, audio, texts, etc. They can also update content metadata or create new ones.
- **Unregistered/unauthenticated users:** These are users who have not registered on the GreenSCENT web platform. They can only view the content generated by registered users and they cannot create new one.
- **GreenSCENT Platform administrator:** This user, commonly referred to as "superuser", is defined during platform setup. They have high-level privileges that allows them to manage the portal and to register and update cultural institutions and their administrative users.

From the point of view of the app:

- GreenSCENT **platform administrator** can't have access to the app.
- **Institution administrators and standard users** are the **same**. The different powers of an administrator can be exercised only from the web interface.

- **Unregistered/unauthenticated user** can **enter the app** and have a look on what is happening on the territory, but they **can’t insert new reports** or **interact with the existing ones**. They can see, but they cannot act.

3.3. Use cases

The basic use cases are the following:

- An institution asks people to monitor a territory searching and reporting on environmental issues.
- Registered GreenSCENT users that belongs to the institutions, insert reports in the platform using the app, attaching multimedia pieces of content. Such new reports are in the state **TO BE APPROVED**.
- The administrator of the institution must verify the reports. They can approve (state of report **APPROVED**) or reject (state of report **REJECTED**) them using the Citizen Journalism web tool (see D3.3, GreenSCENT D3.3-SCENT Platform Technical architecture and user guide).
- Unregistered users using the app can monitor the situation of the territory, but they are not allowed to insert new reports or update the existing ones or interact with registered users.
- Registered users can interact with the current reports (the approved ones) inserting updates about the issues and starting a discussion with other users.
- The owner of a report or the administrator can put a report in **SOLVED** state if they deem the issue is no longer significant in the territory.

Reports can be in the following states: **TO BE APPROVED**, **APPROVED**, **REJECTED**, **SOLVED**. The table shows the possible transitions between them.

Current State	New State	Who can do it
	TO BE APPROVED	Any registered user
TO BE APPROVED	APPROVED	Domain admin (via Citizen Journalism web tool)
TO BE APPROVED	REJECTED	Domain admin (via Citizen Journalism web tool)
APPROVED	SOLVED	User who reported the problem (owner) or institution admin

Table 1 – Environmental reports transition state

The following schema shows the workflow:

Figure 1 - Workflow of states of the reports

3.4. Installation and set-up

It's important to note that for optimal performance, the certified mobile browsers for running the app are **Google Chrome for Android devices** and **Safari for iOS**. Using these browsers ensures a seamless experience with the GreenSCENT mobile application.

To install the mobile app on an **Android device**:

1. Open the Chrome browser on your Android device and enter the following URL: <https://greenscent-app.net/>.
2. Once the page has loaded, look for the icon to access a list of options.
3. Among the options, find and select 'Install App' to initiate the installation process on your device.
4. Follow the on-screen prompts to complete the installation.
5. After the installation is complete, you should see the GreenSCENT icon on your device's main screen.

To install the mobile app on an **iOS device**:

1. Launch the Safari browser on your iOS device and navigate to the URL <https://greenscent-app.net/>.
2. Locate the button and tap on it to reveal additional options.

Figure 2– iOS installation procedure, step 1 and 2

3. From the options presented, choose "Add to Home Screen."

Figure 3– iOS installation procedure, step 3

4. A popup will appear; tap "Add" in the top right corner to confirm and complete the GreenSCENT installation on your iOS device.

Figure 4– iOS installation procedure, step 4

The app requires the authorization to access the GPS position of the device. Below, you will find a brief release note explaining how to activate location services on your iPhone or Android. The procedure on Android devices is very simple. When the app is launched for the first time a dialog box is opened asking the user to authorize geolocation (see figure 8).

Figure 5– Geolocation on Android devices

On iPhones the procedure is more complex and include the following instructions:

- Ensure that the GreenSCENT app is NOT currently running.
- Go to Settings > Safari>Location and confirm that Allow option is set. Please be aware that, to the best of our knowledge, if this option is not accessible, it likely means that Parental Controls have been activated, preventing geolocation. In such a case, you won't be able to use the app to report issues.
- Go to Settings > Privacy & Security > Location Services and make sure that Location Services is on.
- Still in Settings > Privacy & Security > Location Services scroll down to find the app “Safari”.
- Tap the app “Safari” and select an option “Always”.

3.5. Key features

3.5.1. Select Domain (Institution)

First, we need to introduce the concept of domain.

Each institution wishing to use the GreenSCENT services establishes a “domain” and has a separate space on the platform in which to store their content and which the users of the institution are authorized to access.

Each domain has a specific user who acts as the administrator. The administrator manages the space, authorizes new users after self-registration, checks reports, and so on.

GreenSCENT web platform will provide a set of pre-configured domains (e.g., UAB, EA, MAYK, ...) according to the institutions that participate in the project; new ones can be added according to demand. The creation of a new domain can be done only by ENG; it is worth noting that when a new domain is created, the GreenSCENT web-platform will immediately make available a new area for such user's domain to upload multimedia content.

The creation of a new domain is discussed in detail in D3.3 (GreenSCENT D3.3 - SCENT Platform Technical architecture and user guide). Here we discuss how to select the domain in the Environmental Monitoring App. The landing page of the app (even before authentication) asks the users to select the domain they want to enter.

Figure 6– App landing view

Users can see all the available domains by navigating horizontally. They will have to choose one and tap it. Currently the available domains are:

- DBT. Danish Board of Technology
- EA. Ellinogermaniki Agogi
- MAYK. Maunulan yhteiskoulu ja Helsingin matematiikkalukio
- RYT. Royal School of Transylvania
- SMART. Gimnazija Smart

- UAB. Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
- UNIRSM. Università della Repubblica di San Marino
- UNISPMF. University of Novi Sad
- VOLENS. Volens Association, Bucarest

New domains can be added on request.

3.5.2. Homepage and user interface structure

When users have selected a domain, they can get access to the homepage.

Authentication is not necessary to have access to the homepage. So unregistered users can enter the app, select the domain they are interested in and explore all the reports that have been inserted in the platform. However, they are not able to insert new reports or integrate/update the existing ones. They can only view reports and not generate new ones.

Figure 7 – Homepage before/without authentication

All app views share the same structure:

- **Top Navigation Bar** on the top of the screen.
- A **Central Area** containing the main features.

- The **Bottom Navigation Bar** is a consistent element, providing easy navigation between the main features of the app.

Figure 8– User interface structure

Figure 9– Top Navigation Bar

The **TOP Navigation Bar** contains:

- A clickable “GreenSCENT logo”, which redirects users to the landing page when selected.
- A lock icon/avatar that allows login/logout.
- A button that allows users to change the language of the interface. Currently the interface supports five languages: Italian, Catalan, Spanish, Greek, and English.

Clicking on the padlock users can authenticate and get full access to the features of the app.

Figure 10– Authentication using the TOP Navbar

The **Central Area** can show different graphical aspect, representation of data, and kind of information (views) according to the main features of the app. For instance, there is a view dedicated to the presentation of reports in a list, another one dedicated to a representation on a map, yet another dedicated to the insertion of new reports, etc...

The most important views are the ones controlled by the **Bottom Navigation Bar**.

Figure 11– The bottom Navigation Bar

- **List Button:**
 - Function: Access the report list page.
 - Location: Common to all pages.
- **Map Button:**
 - Function: Access a dedicated page displaying reports as markers on a map.
 - Location: Common to all pages.
 - Display: Reports are shown based on their respective coordinates.
- **Personal Button (just for authenticated users):**
 - Function: Access personal reports.
 - Feature: Enabled if the user is logged in.

- Location: Common to all pages.
- **New Button (only for authenticated users):**
 - Function: Create a new report.
 - Feature: Enabled if the user is logged in.

3.5.3. List View

The **List VIEW** is the basic representation of the reports, so it is also considered the homepage of the app.

Here users can see all the reports inserted in the territory in a list of cards. Any card represents a report. In this section only the **reports** in APPROVED state are shown.

Figure 12– LIST View

On the upper part users can find a horizontal scrolling list of tags that represent the **categories** currently **handled by the platform**. Each tag is tappable and works as a filter to show just the reports from a specific category.

Figure 13– Tags

The categories that are currently managed are:

- **#RISK**
- **#EMERGENCY**
- **#POLLUTION**
- **#SOLUTION**

New ones can be added in future when relevant.

Under the list of tags, a vertical scrollable list of cards is shown. Each card represents a report.

Figure 14– Report card

Key information on each card includes:

- **Owner's Avatar** (the avatar of the user who has inserted the report)
- **Report State Icon:** Approved
- **Title of the report**
- **Date and Time** of Submission
- **Distance** from Current Location of the user to the reported issue (this feature does not work if GPS is not active)

Any card is tappable to obtain more information about the issue. See next paragraphs.

3.5.4. Maps View

Using the specific button in the Bottom Navigation Bar, users can view the reports produced, also in map form. Reports are represented on the map based on their respective coordinates.

Here are the main features offered by the view:

- Smoothly managed scrolling and pinch-to-zoom functionalities.
- Users can freely navigate the map and resize it according to their preferences.
- A horizontally scrolling list of reports that is visible on the map.
- Tapping on any marker on the map displays the report card.
- Any card is tappable and provides access to the report detail page.
- A red-outlined marker indicates the location of the selected report.
- The green pinpoint indicates the current position of the user.

Figure 15 – Map View

3.5.5. Detail page

By selecting one of the cards displayed on **LIST view** or in the **MAP view**, the user gains access to the report detail dialog page.

Figure 16 – Detail of a report

This page presents the following features:

- **Owner/creator** (avatar with name beside)
- **Creation** and latest **update date**
- **Title**
- **Tags** for classification
- **Severity** level (low, medium, high)
- **Problem** description

By tapping the workflow icon, the user can see current and pending workflow status.

Figure 17 – Workflow feature

The icons in the lower part allow access to specific features.

Figure 18– Icon bar

The first icon:

- Allows users to view pictures and videos.
- Opens a dedicated dialog page.
- Shows a badge with the current number of multimedia items attached to the report.

Second Icon:

- Provides access to a discussion forum.
- Registered users can modify their own posts.

Last Icon:

- Displays distance from current location to reported issue.
- If tapped, it opens turn by turn navigation to get to the place. It uses the standard navigation app of the mobile device, Google Maps or Apple Maps).

The CLOSE button in the lowest part of the central area closes the detail page.

3.5.6. Personal View

This page is specifically accessible to users who are logged in.

The view shows only the reports created by the logged-in user in any state (so even the ones that have not been approved yet or that have been solved).

The look of the page is almost identical to the LIST VIEW and each report is presented as a card.

Tapping on the card the detail page (paragraph 3.5.5) gets opened.

Figure 19– Personal view

3.5.7. New Report View

To insert a new report, users have to click/tap on the + button on the Bottom Navigation Bar.

Figure 20– + button on the Bottom Navigation Bar

This page is specifically accessible to users who are logged in, allowing them to generate new environmental reports.

Figure 21– NEW REPORT VIEW

So, users are prompted to provide various details:

- Input a concise text in the **"Title"** field for easy report identification.
- Provide a detailed description of the report in the **"Description"** field.
- Select a severity level from the **"Severity"** radio button group.
- Choose one or more tags.
- Click on the **"UPLOAD MULTIMEDIA"** button to upload photos or videos and designate one as the cover image.
- Use the **"CURRENT"** button to geolocate the report based on the current location. Alternatively, tap **"ON MAP"** to choose a different location, with GPS coordinates displayed next to the **"GPS POSITION"** label.

Once all the necessary information is entered, users can create the resource by clicking the **"SEND"** button. The newly created report will promptly appear in the **"Citizen Journalism"** section of the GreenVERSE web portal.

3.6. System requirements

Browser Requirements

- Chrome browser on Android device.
- Safari browser on iOS device.

Internet Requirements

A fast internet connection of at least 30 Mbps is strongly recommended.

4. App Architecture Overview

The **GreenSCENT Environmental Monitoring Mobile App** is a **non-native web app**, displayed through the native browser of the platform (Safari for iOS, Chrome for Android), taking the form of an app. It has been designed as a seamless pipeline that can effectively store and manage various types of **multimedia content**, including **video, photos, documents, and data**, all of which are generated by or made available by the users of the platform.

The figure below offers a summary of the complete GreenSCENT platform, emphasizing the key functional elements and their interconnections. The architecture includes:

- The Storage and distribution facility at the centre of the architecture
- The Environmental Mobile APP
- The Interactive Documentaries tool
- The Citizen Journalism tool
- The administration Interface, dedicated to the general management of the overall platform

So, this is an overall visual representation of the architecture that outlines the components but also features the Environmental Monitoring Mobile App as the principal input interface for the platform.

Whenever a new **environmental report is created**, the mobile app **interacts with the platform using Restful APIs** to transmit the report data seamlessly. As soon as the platform stores the report data, the report becomes instantly accessible and is prepared for further processing.

Figure 22 – GreenSCENT Platform overall architecture

The GreenSCENT web/mobile platform, including the Web Admin interface, the Web User interface, and the Environmental Monitoring App, stands as a **robust web application that can be accessed through all common web browser** (Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, Safari, or others **supporting the HTML 5 standard and WebGL**). Crafted using the MERN stack (MongoDB, Express, React, Node), an open-source middleware stack, this platform facilitates the development of web and mobile interfaces that interact with a complex backend system.

Figure 23 – MERN stack (source: bigscal.com)

To ensure a cohesive and effective system, the platform aligns itself with the widely accepted **three-tier architecture convention**, encompassing a Presentation Layer (frontend interface), an Application Layer (business logic), and a Database Layer. This architectural framework enhances user experience by assigning distinct functions to each tier, allowing for an intuitive and smooth interaction within the system.

Figure 24 – 3 Tier architecture convention

4.1. Presentation Layer

The Presentation Layer serves as the software layer responsible for delivering functionalities related to the user interface and engaging with human users who serve as editors. Its primary function involves connecting

data from the service layer to HTML templates, which are then presented to users on a computer or mobile device through a web browser.

The GreenSCENT web apps (including mobile apps), architecture adopts React and Three.js software libraries.

React is a popular JavaScript library for building user interfaces in web development. It was developed and is maintained by Facebook and is often used for creating single-page applications and dynamic web interfaces. React is utilized to establish connections between the service layer and visual components displayed on the screen.

Three.js is a popular open-source JavaScript library that is used for creating 3D graphics in web development. It is used in creation and visualization of Interactive documentaries. It is cited here because it is part of the overall architecture but has no role in the development of Environmental monitoring app. Three.js simplifies the process of working with WebGL, a low-level API for rendering 3D graphics in web browsers, by providing a higher-level, more user-friendly interface. Three.js has been widely used in web development for creating games, interactive simulations, data visualizations, architectural renderings, product showcases, and more. It provides the tools and capabilities needed to bring 3D content to the web, making it an attractive choice for developers interested in immersive and interactive web experiences. Three.js played a crucial role in synchronizing these components.

Figure 25 – Frontend components

Technically speaking, the Environmental Monitoring app is a non-native web application, so it is displayed through a browser (Safari for iOS, Chrome for Android), but it takes the form of a standard app almost indistinguishable from native ones. This choice has several advantages.

- **Cross-Platform Compatibility:** web technologies like HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, make them inherently cross-platform. A single codebase can be used to target multiple mobile platforms, reducing development time and costs.
- **Faster Development:** as it is possible to leverage existing web development skills and frameworks.
- **Easier Maintenance:** updates and bug fixes are easier to manage, as changes can be made to the central codebase, and users will receive the updates instantly.
- **Improved Accessibility:** web apps are inherently more accessible because they are based on web standards and technologies, so they are easier to make compatible with assistive technologies, ensuring inclusivity for users with disabilities.
- **Wide Distribution:** users do not need to install them from an app store. This lowers the barrier to entry and can result in a larger potential user base.
- **No Store Approval:** unlike native apps, web apps do not need to go through the app stores approval process. This means more control over distribution and updates.

Generally speaking native apps may offer superior performance, access to device-specific features, and a more tailored user experience, while web apps are best suited for projects with limited resources, tight budgets, and a need for broad platform compatibility. The nature of the project drove us toward the adoption of the web technology over the native, as the project is a context in which long-term sustainability, easier maintenance, and minimization of bureaucracy play a more important role than performance or specific advanced features.

4.2. Application Layer

The Application Layer serves as the software layer that oversees the retrieval, processing, transformation, and administration of application data (the business logic). This layer acts as the conductor for the application, executing commands, making logical decisions, conducting evaluations, and executing calculations. Its pivotal function lies in guaranteeing the efficient and effective operation of application logic, tailored to meet user needs.

For the Environmental Monitoring App, the business tier manages user accounts, login credentials, and access control, upholding system security and restricting access to sensitive data to authorized users. Furthermore, the Business Tier handles communication between the user interface and the data storage system. It receives and processes requests from the user interface, retrieves data from the data storage system, and sends the response back to the user interface. This ensures efficient data retrieval and processing, maintaining real-time updates for the user interface.

In summary, the Business Tier is a critical element of the software system, tasked with overseeing application logic, processing data, and harmonizing the interaction between the user interface and the data storage system.

4.3. Database Layer

The Database Layer manages interactions with the Database Management System (DBMS), handling data storage and retrieval from a Database or File System. The fetched information is then sent to the Business Tier for processing before being delivered to the user. To communicate with the DBMS, a set of REST services have been created, utilized by both the web application and external systems (e.g. web apps, mobile apps, etc.).

The database adopted is MongoDB (ver. 5).

MongoDB is a popular, open-source NoSQL (Not Only SQL) database management system known for its flexibility and scalability. It was chosen as the database system in GreenSCENT architecture for several reasons.

- **Document-Oriented:** MongoDB is a document-oriented database, which means it stores data in a format similar to JSON (BSON - Binary JSON). Each data record is a document, and these documents are stored in collections. This ensures consistency and ease of data exchange across system layers. Moreover, using a JSON-like structure, making it easy to work with for those accustomed to JavaScript and related technologies.
- **Schemaless:** Unlike traditional relational databases, MongoDB is schema-less. This means that within a collection, different documents can have different fields and structures, giving you the flexibility to adapt to changing data requirements.
- **Highly Scalable:** MongoDB is designed for horizontal scalability, which means you can easily distribute your data across multiple servers or clusters. This makes it suitable for handling large volumes of data and high-traffic applications.

- **High Performance:** MongoDB is known for its performance, especially in read-heavy workloads. It uses internal memory mapping for data storage, which can significantly speed up data retrieval.
- **Flexible Query Language:** MongoDB supports powerful querying and indexing capabilities, including various query operators, geospatial indexing, and text search. This makes it versatile for a wide range of use cases.
- **Replication and High Availability:** MongoDB supports replica sets, which are groups of MongoDB servers that maintain multiple copies of data to provide high availability and fault tolerance. If one server fails, another can take over seamlessly.
- **Automatic Sharding:** MongoDB can distribute data across multiple servers using automatic sharding. This ensures that your data is distributed evenly and can handle large datasets efficiently.
- **Aggregation Framework:** MongoDB includes a powerful aggregation framework for data processing and transformation, allowing you to perform complex operations on your data within the database.
- **Rich Ecosystem:** MongoDB has a rich ecosystem of tools, libraries, and connectors for various programming languages and platforms. This makes it easy to integrate MongoDB with your existing technology stack.
- **Open Source and Community Support:** MongoDB is open-source, and it has a strong community of users and contributors. This means you can find a wealth of documentation, tutorials, and community support resources.
- **Enterprise Edition:** In addition to the open-source version, MongoDB offers an Enterprise Edition with advanced features, security, and support options for businesses.
- **Cross-Platform Compatibility:** MongoDB is available for various platforms, including Windows, macOS, and numerous Linux distributions, making it versatile for different deployment scenarios.
- **Security Features:** MongoDB offers features for authentication, authorization, encryption, and auditing to help secure data.

Figure 26– MongoDB main characteristics (source: MongoDB)

Overall, MongoDB is a powerful database system that is well-suited for applications with changing and evolving data requirements, as well as those requiring high scalability and performance.

5. Accessibility Features

5.1. Languages supported

The app supports all the official languages of the project. So, the user can choose between the following languages:

- Catalan
- Spanish
- English
- Italian
- Greek

More languages can be added on request.

From any view of the app, the user can tap on the specific command on the top navbar and change the language.

Figure 27– Language choice dialog

We chose not to use flags in the language selector. Even though languages are often represented by flags, this choice can be problematic. Flags represent a country and not necessarily the language spoken in that country. This can lead to confusion and misunderstanding when it comes to representing different languages.

According to recommendations of **Web Content Accessibility Guidelines** (WCAG advises against using flags as a sole means of indicating language choice. It emphasizes the importance of providing clear, understandable text labels or language codes alongside flags to cater to a diverse and inclusive audience) and the **United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities** ([...using flags exclusively for language selection may hinder accessibility and can be considered a violation of these principles.]), we chose to adopt the name of the language in its native script with its ISO 639-1 two-letter code.

Here is a list of arguments against the use of flags to identify a language:

1. **Language and Location Are Not the Same:** Flags are often associated with countries or regions, but languages and regions do not always align. A country can have multiple languages, and multiple countries can share the same language.
2. **Exclusion and Misrepresentation:** When flags are used to represent languages, it can exclude users who don't identify with the flag of the country associated with their language. For instance, a Spanish speaker from Mexico might not appreciate being presented with the flag of Spain.
3. **Inaccessibility:** For blind users, flags can be meaningless. Screen readers, which are commonly used by blind people, won't interpret flags as language choices, potentially leaving these users unable to access content in their preferred language.
4. **Language Diversity:** Flags don't account for all the languages spoken around the world. There are thousands of languages, and not all of them are associated with a country or flag.
5. **Linguistic Preferences:** People in multilingual countries may have strong linguistic preferences and may not appreciate being forced into a language choice based on their location.
6. **User Confusion:** Using flags for language selection can lead to user confusion, as they might not immediately understand its relation to language choice.

Here is a sample of the look of a section of the app in Greek.

Figure 28– New View in Greek

5.2. Other accessibility features

As the Environmental Monitoring app is not a native app, but a web app executed through the native browser of the platform (Safari for iOS, Chrome for Android) other accessibility features have been implemented using the native features included in the browsers and in the OS.

Mobile versions of Safari and Chrome, like other modern web browsers, incorporate various accessibility features to ensure that people with disabilities can access and interact with web content effectively. These features help enhance the usability and inclusivity of the browser for individuals with different needs. Here are the key accessibility features that can be activated in the latest versions of the operative systems.

VoiceOver: VoiceOver is a built-in screen reader that reads aloud the contents of the web page, making it accessible to blind users. VoiceOver can also provide spoken descriptions of images and other non-text content.

Dynamic Type: This allows users to adjust the text size and font to suit their reading preferences and needs. This feature benefits partially blind individuals or those who may need larger text for better readability.

High Contrast Mode: Users can enable high contrast mode to enhance the visibility of content on websites. This mode increases the contrast between text and background colours, making it easier to read for individuals with low vision.

Web Content Zoom: Users can zoom in and out on web content to increase its size, making it more accessible for those with partial blindness or difficulties reading small text.

Alternative Text for Images: Web developers can provide alternative text for images in their websites. This alt text is read aloud by screen readers, providing descriptions of images for users who cannot see them.

Voice Control: a feature that allows users to control their device and navigate web content using voice commands. This feature can be especially helpful for people with reduced mobility.

Safari on iOS and Chrome on Android place a strong emphasis on accessibility to ensure that users with a range of abilities can enjoy a seamless and inclusive browsing experience. These features not only benefit individuals with disabilities but also contribute to the overall usability and user-friendliness of websites and web apps for a broader audience.

Figure 29– Example of the Main page (List view) on iOS with colour inversion option enabled.

6. Conclusion

The GreenSCENT mobile app aims to offer a tool that allows environmental issue tracking. Its primary objective is to empower individuals and communities to proactively monitor and address environmental concerns. Through the mobile app, users can generate detailed issue reports, encompassing a comprehensive description of the problem, severity level, and relevant multimedia, such as photos or videos for visual evidence. Leveraging GPS technology, the app automatically captures and associates geographical coordinates with each report, facilitating precise location tracking.

This document reports the technical architecture of the Environmental Monitoring app that is the demonstrator developed in the T3.3 of WP3. It describes its main components, their interactions, and the features that each one offers. Moreover, it provides a user guide about installation and use of the app.

The UI is described in detail, so the document can also be considered as a handbook for the mobile app.